

CITY OF HELSINKI
 Education Division
 Client Fees and Invoicing
 PO BOX 51301, 00099 CITY OF HELSINKI

INCOME DECLARATION

For the determination of the client fee
Enquiries: Education Division,
switchboard tel. 09 310 8600
 (telephone service hours 9–11)

Received

Child's name and personal identity code	Location of early childhood education
Parents / guardians / unmarried or married partners living in the same household and their personal identity codes	
Other children in the family and their dates of birth	

We agree to pay the highest fee and return the signed form without income details to the Client Fees unit.

INCOME DETAILS AND APPENDICES ARE PROVIDED With incomplete income details, the fee can be set at the highest amount	Gross monthly income of the guardian, married/unmarried partner	Gross monthly income of the guardian, married/unmarried partner
Earned and additional income (appendix: most recent payslip or a pay certificate from the employer, showing the income accumulated over several months)		
– fringe benefits		
– holiday bonus		
Pensions		
Unemployment benefits, integration allowance, sickness allowance		
Maternity allowance, parental allowance, child care allowance or flexible/partial care allowance		
Child maintenance/support for the youngest child in early childhood education, orphan's pension		
Other income (e.g. grants, job alternation compensation, support for informal care, start-up grant)		
Entrepreneur's income (shareholder of a limited liability company: attach a pay statement and a statement of the fringe benefits and dividends; private entrepreneur: attach an income statement and balance sheet; general or limited partnership: attach an income statement, balance sheet and a statement of the pay and fringe benefits)		
Capital gains: interest and dividend income		
Rental income (excluding the management charge) Appendix: rental agreement and management charge invoice		
Studies: student allowances, adult education subsidy		
Reductions: child maintenance paid (copy of the proof of payment)		

I hereby declare that the above information is true and consent to the information being verified with different authorities, such as the Incomes Register, if necessary. The Tax Administration's Incomes Register will be used to verify the applicant's salary income, certain benefits and pensions, while other income (see above) must be declared with the relevant information and documents (the information in the application will be processed confidentially). The guardian is obligated to notify the Client Fees unit of any changes to income, expenditure or family size.

Guardian: I consent to my income details being checked in the Incomes Register.

Second guardian / married or unmarried partner: I consent to my income details being checked in the Incomes Register.

Place and date Guardian's signature, name in block letters, telephone number and e-mail address

Place and date Second guardian's / married or unmarried partner's signature, name in block letters, telephone number and e-mail address

The income declaration and its appendices must be submitted within two weeks of the start of early childhood education to the above address or by secure email or left at the child's early childhood education location to be delivered onwards. With incomplete income details, the fee can be set at the highest amount.

The fee is charged from the date of commencement of early childhood education in accordance with the decision.

Any changes in income, expenditure or family size must be reported to the above address.